

JUST IN TIME INVENTORY MANAGEMENT PRACTICES AND SUPPLY CHAIN PERFORMANCE OF FOAM MANUFACTURING COMPANIES IN KWARA STATE NIGERIA.

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Abstract

Just in time is the way to improve efficiency. This study explored the just in time inventory management practices and supply chain performance of foam manufacturing companies in Kwara, state Nigeria. The specific objectives are to; assess the effect of quality control on the supply chain performance of foam manufacturing companies in Kwara, state Nigeria and investigate the effect of suppliers' relationship on the supply chain performance of foam manufacturing companies in Kwara state Nigeria. There are two foam manufacturing firms in Kwara state, and 517 employees form the population of this study. The study used the Taro Yamane formula to determine a sample size of 225. A closed-ended questionnaire was used for data collection. The statistical tool used for analysis was descriptive statistics that is (frequency, percentage, mean, and standard deviation) and SPSS software version 25 was used for regression. The results show a positive and significant relationship between quality control and supply chain performance, and the suppliers' relationship shows a positive and significant relationship with supply chain performance. The study concluded that there is a significant relationship between just in time inventory management practices and chain performance of foam manufacturing companies in Kwara State, Nigeria. The study recommends that supplier partners should be actively involved in the quality control process of foam manufacturing companies in Kwara State, Nigeria.

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1.0 Introduction

With the fast-changing consumer market, which is acting on globalization, firms are under pressure to be up to the newest trends and innovate by offering new goods and keeping total production costs low. Just in time necessitates a flexible supply chain that can be used to produce other items as well as for future ventures. By simplifying production processes, the Just in Time philosophy encourages waste reduction. Excess stocks are also attenuated or eliminated, and resources are used additionally with efficiency by reducing setup times, controlling material flows, and stressing preventative maintenance. (Shivaani., et al. 2021)

At first, just in time inventory management was an inventory management control technique that required the organization to maintain zero inventories. However, the use of just in time inventory has evolved to incorporate management principles like kaizen (continuous improvement), inventory management, quality management, use of technology (ERP), employee involvement, waste elimination, and supplier relationship management. The above new concepts have facilitated organizations to focus on the ultimate objective of JIT delivery, smoothly synchronized continuous flow (purchasing and production) keyed to final demand, perfect quality of incoming materials, goods in-process, and finished products (Kootanaee et al, 2013).

Furthermore, Franco and Rubha (2020) stated that the true definition of the concept of just-in-time is that the production of one unit of a product to be transferred for just in time is a subsequent process that must proceed. The purpose of just in time inventory management is to produce a unit in such a way that there is only one unit of work in process and a minimum stock of finished goods in inventory. The supply chain system is a type of management strategy that directly influences the supplier's raw material orders during the production cycle. Companies use the Just in time strategy to enhance their effectiveness and reduce losses by receiving goods only during the production to ensure minimal losses, thereby reducing inventory costs (Digvijay & Anil, 2019). Producing only as much as required, in the smallest possible batches, with the fewest errors allowed, and in possibly short cycles, is the basis for the successful implementation of a just-in-time inventory management strategy by manufacturing companies. Customer orders will always dictate the course of the process, determine what will be procured and to what extent, as well as what will be produced and in what period, while neutralizing the costs of keeping stocks of materials and finished products. The organizational structure that encourages the commitment and teamwork of employees in the processes of planning, organizing, and controlling is one of the key factors for the success of production without warehousing/stocking, as production based on the just in time principle is often called. (Jelena et al., 2022)

It has been confirmed that organizations worldwide adopted just in time inventory management systems into their operations (Ralahallo, 2021). However, despite the increasing attention given to just in time inventory management in academic and practical fields, the performance of manufacturing firms in Nigeria, including foam manufacturing, has been very unsatisfactory. Jelena et al (2022) indicated that manufacturing firms in Nigeria have a problem with inaccurate forecasts, mainly because they lack real-time inventory information about customers' demand. This has, in turn, led to late deliveries, inadequate deliveries, and a lack of consistency in the delivery of products, thus leading to lack of customer satisfaction. Foam manufacturing firms operating in Nigeria are facing problems in determining appropriate inventory levels that should be kept to ensure that customer needs are met just in time and that the production process is not interrupted. Investment in just in time inventories, such as technologies and strategic supplier's partners creates opportunity for foam manufacturing firms to gain market advantage by outperforming competitors in terms of attracting more customers with distinguished products and charging premium prices (Hoffman, 2024). Foam manufacturing companies in Nigeria also experience problems related to investments in less critical stocks, leading to unnecessary costs, inaccurate forecasts, and poor responsiveness to customer orders, leading to declining performance (Hassein & Zayed 2020).

In light of these, this study addresses whether just in time inventory management practices of quality control and supplier relationships have any effect on supply chain performance among foam manufacturing companies in Kwara state, Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The main objectives of this study are to;

- i. assess the effect of quality control on supply chain performance of foam manufacturing companies in Kwara state of Nigeria
- ii. investigate the effect of supplier's relationship effect on supply chain performance of foam manufacturing companies in Kwara state of Nigeria

Statement of the Hypothesis

- i. **H₀₁:** There is no significant effect between quality control and supply chain performance of foam manufacturers in the Kwara State of Nigeria.
- ii. **H₀₂:** There is no significant effect between suppliers' relationships and supply chain performance of foam manufacturers in the Kwara State of Nigeria.

2.0 Literature Review

The philosophy of just in time (JIT) inventory management is mostly related to the manufacturing industry, which has the plans to dispose of waste. Waste results from any action which adds cost to the process of production or giving out services without essentially increasing the value of the item being produced or service being given. An example is the transportation inventories from one distribution center to the next or the basic demonstration of putting them into storage (Madanhire & Mbohwa, 2016). Sustaining the advantage that the organization has over its competition is the main objective of just in time inventory management. Just in time inventory management is well accomplished by focusing on the customers and delivering an exceptionally superior performance while keeping the cost of production of goods and services at a minimum level and continuously improving quality (Chen, 2023). One of the main reasons is that just in time is a tool mostly used for inventory management systems and that it has been successful over the years. However, the financial implications of just in time inventory management are very critical. Juárez *et al.* (2017)

For years now, just in time, inventory management applications have been effective and efficient within manufacturing sectors globally. This has led to the adoption and implementation of the philosophy within service industries, not only in the manufacturing industries (Hay, 2018). In the successful implementation and execution of just-in-time inventory management, manufacturing companies can counter the vulnerability they face due to the regularly changing financial climate. Based on research of Khourshed and Youssef (2024) that measure the relationship between inventory level and organizational effectiveness through JIT, the technique has played major roles and had a drastic impact on agencies that had to manage their finances (costs specifically). However, for the context of this research, the question is whether foam manufacturers are among those organizations that have adopted the philosophy and benefited.

Quality Control

Quality Control (QC) is a system that is used to maintain the optimal desired level of quality in a product or service. It can also be considered a systematic control of various factors that affect product quality. It depends on materials, tools, machines, labour type been used, working conditions and so on. Quality control is a very broad term; it involves inspection at all stages of production(s) but just mere inspection does not mean quality control. As opposed to inspection, in quality control activity, emphasis is placed on the quality of future production. Quality control aims at prevention of defects at the source and relies on an effective feedback system and corrective action procedures. Quality control uses inspection as a valuable tool (Khawarita & Elvira 2020)

According to Joesph, (2021) “Quality control is the regulatory process through which it measures the actual quality performance of a product or services, compare it with standards, and act but not just looking at the difference”. Another definition of quality control according to Standards Organization of Nigeria (SON) 2020 standard quality control is defined as “The operational techniques and the activities which sustain a quality of product or service that will satisfy given needs; also the use of such techniques and activities”. Armin et al., (2020) defined quality control “in the broad sense that the quality control is the mechanism by which products or services are made to measure up to specifications determined from customers, demands and transformed into sales engineering and manufacturing requirements, it is concerned with making things right rather than discovering and rejecting those made wrong”. According to Fotopoulos, and Evangelos. (2020), quality control is a comprehensive and structured approach to organizational management that seeks to improve the quality of products and services with ongoing refinements in response to continuous feedback. Quality control is part of the combination of inventory control, quality control, and production management functions that make up quality management that make efforts for quality improvement by two ways. First, it concentrates on the philosophical aspects of quality improvement by making quality everyone’s responsibility and then focuses on the effective implementation of quality control techniques. It recognizes that the most valuable resources of an organization are its workers. Workers work best when they are motivated, valued, encouraged to contribute, and allowed to make their own decisions. Under this approach, workers inspect the product quality after each successive operation. They are trained in the preparation and interpretation of process control charts along with managers. Managers motivate workers to think of quality first and production rate second. The workers have the authority to halt the production line or cell if quality problems arise. Thus, this concept not only gives quality responsibility to workers but also matches that responsibility with authority to share the quality control functions so that quality problems can be identified and solved quickly (Kumar, 2020).

Suppliers Relationship

The supplier relationship (SR) is a management approach that manages all interactions between an organization and its suppliers (Khaing, 2019). Suppliers in this context refer to any organization that sells something (mostly materials) to the organization that runs the supplier relationship management application. The primary goal of supplier relationship management is to improve the efficiency and effectiveness of inter-organizational processes, with the delivery of superior value to customers taking precedence. Previously, the customer was the primary focus of organizations forgetting the fact that to satisfy the customer in a competitive environment, the supplier relationship must be looked into. The supplier has grown in importance with the global sourcing of non-core operations. Suppliers were handled adversarially, with transactional techniques predominating. However, the growth of information communication systems, total quality management, and industrial restructuring shift buyer behaviour from transactional to cooperative strategies (Zhang, & Cao, 2018). Good collaboration with suppliers produces more perks than opportunism for one party.

Strategy suppliers in the twenty-first millennium are more reliant on their resource base and technologies. Firms depend on strategy suppliers’ relationships to increase quality, lower costs, and build innovative products and processes faster than competitors (Zhang, et al., 2020). They also add value to a company by providing access to technology, markets, and information (Chen, 2023). All of this has compelled firms to handle suppliers strategically. Olusanya, (2018) explained supplier relationship management as a method and style of effective communicating with suppliers. According to supply chain experts, SRM is a comprehensive design for defining what a supplier demands from a supplier and managing the connectivity between companies to reach the required necessities (Matunga et al., 2021). SRM bridges the gap between the organization and the end-user. Companies face difficulties in their network chains, resulting in loss of business. It is recommended that such companies find

and implement supplier relationship management practices to improve their supply chain efficiency (Matunga et al., 2021).

Supply Chain Performance

Supply chain performance creates profitable business margins for industries and provide best outcomes in services to the customers (Alshurideh, et al, 2022). It also creates customer experiences and attitudes toward the products and holds their interests for a longer time. The performance -based structure of the supply chain helps to maintain the criteria in which the accuracy of the time management is considered for delivering products to its customers (Al Batyneh, et al, 2022). Currently, business industries have become efficient in meeting the market requirements in terms of customer demand, and they are also taking initiative to perform supply chain strategies to fulfill the customer needs at their door step (Farouk, 2022). The supply chain performance measurement is a task of the supply chain management of the business industries that defines the operational activities of the business (Shamout, et al, 2022). Supply chain performance starts with the manufacturing of raw materials to deliver the items to consumers' hands (Eli, & Lalla 2022). It depends only on efficient supply chain management that holds the entire business industry and its operations through different strategic networks (Al Kurdi, et al, 2020).

Cost Efficiency

Kinyugo (2021) argued that cost efficiency deals with cost reduction as well as continuous improvement product with the least waste while also having the best resources and change instead of cost containment. The term cost reduction can could be used in place of cost efficiency. Cost efficiency refers to actions taken by managers to reduce costs, some of which are prioritized on the basis of information extracted from the accounting system. Kinyugo (2021) noted that although traditional cost control systems have been applied on a continuous basis in organizations, cost efficiency tends to be applied on an ad hoc basis whenever an opportunity for cost reduction is identified. Similarly, the majority of the approaches that are incorporated within the area of cost efficiency do not necessarily involve the use of accounting techniques. In contrast, cost control relies heavily on accounting techniques. Measuring cost reduction by evaluating whether manufacturers' costs are higher, equal, or lower than their industrial competitors. In addition, manufacturers were asked whether they were lagging, below averaged, average, above, or leaders in the industry in terms of meeting customers' requirements. Sabure (2020) added that three types of costs must be considered in setting inventory levels: holding costs, ordering costs, and stock-out costs.

Empirical Review

Samer et al., (2022) conducted a conceptual and empirical review of the impact of just in time strategy and pull chain strategy on supply chain performance. The study using both conceptual and empirical review analyzed 11 studies that lead to the findings that supply chan's enchands the overall competitive performance of organization and that it provided advance authority to the idea that using the just in time and pull strategy strategies will increase organizational performance by fortifying supply chain connections with recommendation of organizations to also put in more effort on just in time and pull strategy strategies.

Ralahallo (2021) conducted a study aimed at determining the effect of just in time and supply chain management (SCM) on company performance at seafood restaurants in Ambon city. The population of the study is some restaurants in Ambon city that gets fish supply. The data for this study were obtained from questionnaires filled out by 35 respondents at 20 seafood restaurants in Ambon city. Data collection techniques in this study used a questionnaire. Multiple linear regression analysis was used to test the hypothesis. The results show that just in time had a positive and significant effect on company performance, and supply chain management had a positive and significant effect on company performance. It was recommended that both just in time and supply chain should also be put in the front of seafood restaurants.

George and Elrashid (2023) investigated the role of inventory level control and demand forecasting on the pharmaceutical supply chain (PSC) performance of hospital pharmacies. Data were collected from 171 respondents working in private hospitals in Bahrain with the use of survey questionnaire and was analyzed with the use structural equation modeling approach. The study found a significant positive relationship between inventory level control and PSC performance. Similarly, the relationship between demand forecasting and PSC performance is positive and significant. The research has implications for practice, including assisting hospital pharmacies in identifying the best practices to manage pharmaceutical inventory and understanding the impact of inventory control and demand forecasting on PSC performance to ensure zero stock outs and withstand fluctuations in demand and supply. The findings reveal a significant relationship between inventory level control and pharmaceutical supply chain performance and a significant relationship between demand forecasting and pharmaceutical supply chain performance. It was recommended for hospitals and health care providers to establish an appropriate PSC system in other to make better decisions regarding medicine supply.

Salim et al., (2023) investigated the strategic inventory management practices adopted by logistics organizations in Oman, including demand forecasting, procurement optimization, and inventory control techniques as proxies to strategic inventory management practices. Using indicators such as order fulfillment, on-time delivery, inventory turnover, and customer satisfaction as performance proxies, specifically within the context of the Omani logistics industry. The explorative research design and the study highlight the significance of a well-designed inventory management strategy in enhancing overall organizational performance by improving resource allocation, minimizing stock outs, and enhancing supply chain responsiveness. The study found practical implications for logistics managers in Oman and recommended that order fulfillment, on-time delivery, inventory turnover such be practices in the Omani context.

Anthony (2023) analyzed the impact of inventory management practices on the overall organization performance. A case of Halsted builders express, Bulawayo Zimbabwe. A cross-sectional survey research method was employed. The study population is 100 employees, and the sample size is 80. Based on the data collected from the questionnaire, interviews, observations, and focus group discussions. The finding of the study shows that the organization through establishing supplier relationships has optimized risk management, thereby enhancing organizational performance. Inventory management helps companies identify which and how much stock to order at what time. The study also indicated that sourcing has assisted us to reduce direct and indirect costs, sourcing has assisted the organization to mitigate supplier risks, and sourcing has improved our relationships with customers and chain management. Our organization has collaborated with the best suppliers. The recommendation was for organizations to also involve suppliers in their activities in other to have better overall performance.

Mohammed et al., (2021) investigated the effects of supplier JIT on flexibility performance and explored the moderating impacts of advanced manufacturing technology (AMT) and human resource empowerment (EMP). This study uses hierarchical linear regression analysis with data collected form 213 manufacturing firma in China. Findings revealed a negative influence of suppliers' JIT on flexibility performance but adopted AMT and EMP to reconcile the conflict between supplier JIT and flexibility performance. The recommendation was for the manufacturing firm to eliminate supplier JIT because of its negative effect on flexible performance but to keep both AMT and EMP.

Theoretical Framework

Transaction Cost Economy Theory (TCE)

Ronald Coase and Oliver E. Williamson, an American economist founded the theory in 1950, analysed the cost associated with economic transactions. The TCE looked at transaction costs associated with planning, adapting,

and monitoring economic transactions that are self-interest seeking behaviour of individuals and firms that can lead to transaction costs. The transaction cost economics theory attempts to answer is 'why firms exist'? In the context of supply chain performance, the transaction cost economy aims to reduce the costs associated with conducting a transaction when deciding whether to make or buy a transaction.

According to Williamson (2021), a transaction cost occurs "when a good or service is transferred across a technologically separable interface". Therefore, transaction costs arise every time a product or service is transferred from one stage to another, where new sets of technological capabilities are needed to make the product or service. Transaction costs related to resource exchange with the external environment can reflected the following factors. The list is not exhaustive; environmental uncertainty, opportunism, risks, bounded rationality, and core company assets.

The factors above will all potentially increase external transaction costs, which may become rather expensive for a company to control. Therefore, it may very well be more economical to maintain the activity in-house so that the company will not use resources on e.g. contracts with suppliers, meetings, and supervision. Therefore, if companies see environmental uncertainty as high, they might choose not to outsource or exchange resources with the environment.

3.0 Methodology

This study adopted the descriptive survey research method, which is a systematic collection of data in standardized form from an identifiable population. The descriptive survey was effective for this study because it sought to understand the relationship between just in time inventory and supply chain performance.

The population of this study was made up of employees of foam manufacturing companies that have a manufacturing plant in Kwara state in Nigeria, which according to the manufacturers association of Nigeria (MAN) (2024) are two (2) as shown in the table 1.

Table 1. Population of the Study

S/N	Foam Manufacturers	Location	No. of employees
1	United Foam LTD	Ilorin, Kwara	269
2	Vita Foam Nigeria PLC	Ilorin, Kwara	248
	Total		517

Source: Researcher's Computation

From the two (2) foam manufacturing companies, there are a total of five hundred and seventeen (517) employees. The research adopted the use of Taro Yamane (1967) formula to determine the sample size. According to Smith (1984) in sample size determination in agreement with Taro Yamane sample size determination technique (1967), which stated that when the population is above four hundred (400), there is a need to use the Taro Yamane formula to reduce the population.

According to Yamane (1967), the sample size of a study can be calculated as follows:

$$n = N/1+N(e)^2$$

Where N = population size.

e = the margin of error (assumed at 5%)

$$1 = \text{constant}$$

$$n = 517/1+517(0.05)^2$$

$$n = 517/1+517(0.0025)$$

$$n = 517/1+1.2925$$

$$n = 517/2.2925$$

n = 225.517

n = 225

Table 2 Sample Size

S/N	Foam Manufacturers	Location	No. of employees	of Sample Using Formula	Allocation Burnley's	Sample Size
4	United Foam LTD	Ilorin, Kwara	269	$\frac{269(225)}{517}$	60,525 517	= 117
5	Vita Foam Nigeria PLC	Ilorin, Kwara	248	$\frac{248(225)}{517}$	55,800 517	= 108
	Total		51			225

Source: Researcher's Computation

Table 2 shows the sample size of the study after proportional allocation was done to get the number of questionnaire to be distributed to the two different foam manufacturing companies in Kwara state Nigeria with United foam Ilorin, Kwara state having one hundred seventeen (117), and Vita foam Ilorin, Kwara state having one hundred and eight (108).

The researcher used a questionnaire to gather primary data from the target population for foam manufacturing companies. The questionnaire was designed on a five (5) point Likert type scale to collect data from the respondents.

Multiple regression was performed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) Version 25 to analyze data obtained from the study. The researcher used testes such as t-test and f-test for the probability of either accepting or rejecting hypotheses based on the condition of 5% level of significant.

Model Specification

$$SCP = \beta_0 + \beta_1QC + \beta_2SR + E$$

Where:

SCP = Supply Chain Performance

QC = Quality Control

SR = Suppliers Relationship

β_0 = is the intercept of the performance regression model.

E = Error term associated with model

$\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4$ and β_5 are the rate of change of the just in time inventory variables with respect to the supply chain performance variable.

Descriptive Statistics

This section provides descriptive statistics of the variables of the study using the mean and standard deviation. The result is presented on table 3.

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics of Variables

Variables	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Supply Chain Performance	4.63	0.730	161
Suppliers Relationship	4.46	0.837	161
Quality Control	3.88	0.696	161

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 3 presents the descriptive statistics of the variables of the study. The variables are supply chain performance, suppliers' relationships, and quality control. All variables were measured using a five-point Likert scale. Supply chain performance shows a mean of 4.63 and a standard deviation of 0.730, indicating that the majority of respondents strongly agreed to the statement on the questionnaire about supply chain performance. Supplier relationship has a mean of 4.46 and a standard deviation of 0.837, which show that majority of the respondents agreed to the statement on supplier's relationship in the questionnaire. Quality control has a mean of 3.88 and a standard deviation of 0.696, which show that majority of the respondents agreed to the statement on quality control.

Regression Results

The regression results show the effect of each independent variable on the dependent variable. The regression coefficient values indicate the extent of the effect, which ranges from 0% to 100%. This section presents the F statistics, R^2 , and adjusted R^2 of the model.

Dependent Variable: Supply Chain Performance				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. error	t-statistic	prob.t
(Constant)	1.948	0.277	7.027	0.000
Suppliers Relationship	0.223	0.073	3.040	0.003
Quality Control	0.436	0.088	4.934	0.000
R squared	.380			
Adj. R squared	.372			
F statistics	48.351			
Prob. (R - squared)	0.000			

Table 4: Regression Results

Source: SPSS v25.

Table 4 presents the regression results of the model. The model consists of the dependent variable supply chain performance and independent variables (i.e., suppliers' relationship and quality control). In the model, the multiple coefficients of determination R^2 is 0.380. This means that 38.0% of the change in supply chain performance was caused by changes in independent variables, whereas the remaining 62% of the change in supply chain performance was caused by other factors not included in the model. The f-statistics is 48.351 with a p-value of 0.000, which is less than 0.05 and is statistically significant, which means the model is fit because it accounts for the variation in the dependent variable.

The effect of the independent variable suppliers' relationship on the dependent variable supply chain performance is positive with the coefficient value of 0.256, meaning that a unite increase in suppliers' relationship while other variables remain constant leads to an increase in supply chain performance by 25.6%. The effect of the independent variable, quality control, on the dependent variable supply chain performance is positive, with a coefficient value of 0.415, meaning that a unite increase in quality control while other variables remain constant leads to an increase in supply chain performance by 41.5%

Hypothesis Testing

In other to decide whether to reject or accept the null hypothesis at 0.05 (5%) level of significant, the rejection point is use which state that. (1) If the p value is equal to or less than 5%, the null hypotheses is rejected and the alternate hypotheses is accepted; (2) If the p value is more than 5%, the null hypotheses is accepted and the alternate hypothesis is rejected.

Quality Control and Supply Chain Performance

The t-statistic of quality control was 4.934, with a p-value of 0.000, which is less than 0.05. Therefore; the null hypothesis one which state that there is no significant relationship between quality control and supply chain performance of foam manufacturing companies in Kwara state Nigeria is rejected.

Suppliers Relationship and Supply Chain Performance

The t-statistic of supplier's relationship is 3.040 with a p-value of 0.003, which is less than 0.05. Therefore; the null hypothesis 2, which states that there is no significant relationship between supplier relationship and supply chain performance of foam manufacturing companies in Kwara State Nigeria, is rejected.

Discussion of Findings

Most of the reviewed studies confirmed that just in time inventory management practices has a direct and considerable effect on supply chain performance. In this study, quality control was found to have a significant effect on supply chain performance. This is in agreement with the study of George and Elrashid (2023), who investigated the role of inventory level control and demand forecasting on the pharmaceutical supply chain (PSC) performance of hospital pharmacies and found a significant positive relationship between inventory level control and PSC performance.

The supplier's relationship was found to have a significant effect on supply chain performance. This is in agreement with the study of Anthony (2023), who analyzed the impact of inventory management practices on the overall performance of the organization in Halsted builders express, Bulawayo, Zimbabwe and found that the organization, through establishing supplier relationships, has optimized risk management, thereby enhancing organizational performance.

Conclusions Recommendation

This study concluded that inventory management practices just in time had a significant effect on supply chain performance. Quality control has a direct and significant effect on supply chain performance, as observed from the standardization of inputs, workflows, and outputs, which are all quality standards. The supplier relationship has a direct and significant effect on supply chain performance, which can be seen as there are always timeliness and deliveries by suppliers because of their relationship.

This study recommends that suppliers' partners should be actively involved in the quality control process of foam manufacturing companies in Kwara State, Nigeria. Input, workflow, and output processes should be standardized in foam manufacturing companies in Kwara State, Nigeria. The study also recommends that foam manufacturing companies in the Kwara state strive to build long-term relationships with suppliers by giving them a percentage profit margin.

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